

QUINOLINE DERIVATIVES. PART II.

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Antipyrine, discovered by Knorr in 1887, has greater antipyretic activity than quinine, but has no specific action against malaria. It was, therefore, thought that, if a quinoline derivative with fused pyrazolone ring could be synthesised, such a compound will have antipyretic activity and, at the same time, is expected to possess antimalarial properties, due to the presence of the quinoline residue.

Knorr and Jödicke (*Ber.*, 1885, 18, 2262) obtained a pyrazolinoquinoline by reducing the product obtained from *o*-nitrobenzoylacetoacetic ester and phenylhydrazine. Narang, Rây and Singh (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 427) synthesised a pyrazolinoquinoline derivative, the pharmacological examination of which is still under investigation.

It has been thought worth while to explore other new methods for the synthesis of pyrazolinoquinolines. With this object in view, 1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazolone has been condensed with anthranilic acid at 130-140° in presence of fused sodium acetate, when the pyrazolinoquinoline derivative (I) is obtained with the elimination of two molecules of water.

(I)

(II)

Although 6-aminoquinoline and 8-aminoquinoline have no action on paramacia in strength of 1 : 4000, the introduction of OH-group into these quinoline derivatives raises their toxic action on paramacia to a remarkable degree (Brahmachari, *et al.*, *J. Pharm. Expt. Therap.*, 1931, 41, 255 ; 1932, 44, 445). With this idea in view, an investigation was started for the synthesis of some aminohydroxyquinoline derivatives, so that their anti-malarial action can be studied. Urethanylacetic ester has now been condensed with *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde in presence of acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate, when α -urethanyl-*o*-nitrocinnamic ester (II) is obtained. The compound (II) on reduction was expected to give

α -hydroxy- β -carbethoxyaminoquinoline and subsequent hydrolysis would give 2-hydroxy-3-aminoquinoline.

Reduction of the compound (II) with zinc dust and acetic acid did not proceed smoothly. An impure product was obtained, which, however, could not be crystallised. With tin and hydrochloric acid, the compound yields the hydrochloride of *o*-aminocinnamic acid with the disruption of the urethanyl group.

With a view to synthesise $\alpha\gamma$ -diketo- β -aminobenzoyltetrahydroquinoline, hippuric acid has now been condensed with anthranilic acid at 145-150° in presence of fused sodium acetate, when a mixture of the anilide of hippuric acid and a compound possessing the composition $C_{16}H_{12}O_3N_2$ is obtained. That the latter compound possesses the structure (III) is proved by the fact that it contains a reactive methylene group and condenses with aldehyde to give the compound (IV).

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

*Condensation of 1-Phenyl-3-methylpyrazolone with Anthranilic Acid: Formation of 1-Phenyl-3-methylpyrazoline-4:5 (2':3')-4'-hydroxyquinoline (I).—*An intimate mixture of 1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazolone (8.7 g.) and anthranilic acid (6.8 g.) was fused at 130-140° and finely powdered fused sodium acetate (6 g.) was slowly added during 1 hour. The mass was heated at 130-140° for 4 hours. On cooling, it was treated with aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution. The filtered mass was next treated with cold dilute alkali, a small portion remaining undissolved. The alkaline solution, on acidification with excess of hydrochloric acid, yielded a reddish brown pasty mass which was triturated with alcohol. The alcoholic solution left a precipitate free from pasty matter, which crystallised from large quantity

of alcohol in slender yellowish needles, m.p. 175-76°, yield 1 g. (Found: C, 73.82; H, 5.11; N, 15.48. $C_{17}H_{13}ON_3$ requires C, 74.18; H, 4.72; N, 15.27 per cent). When boiled with strong hydrochloric acid or with a mixture of strong hydrochloric acid and glacial acetic acid, it remains unchanged. This shows that the compound, under these conditions, does not form a hydrochloride and, in this respect, resembles the compound of Knorr and Jödicke (*loc. cit.*). It is insoluble in aqueous bicarbonate but soluble in dilute alkali and precipitated by acids. It gives a dark brown colouration with ferric chloride.

The alkali-insoluble product crystallised from alcohol in light yellow needles, m. p. 142-43°. (Found: N, 11.97, 11.81). When boiled with strong hydrochloric acid for about 1 hour, it yields a hydrochloride (colourless stout needles), m.p. 95-96°. Further studies of the compound were not possible due to its extremely poor yield.

o-Urethanyl-*o*-nitrocinnamic Ester (II).—An acetic anhydride solution of urethanylacetic ester (8.8 g., b.p. 161°/90 mm.), *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde (7.6 g.) and fused sodium acetate (5 g.) was heated under reflux for about 4 hours. On cooling and standing overnight, the deep red solution deposited a crystalline product, which was filtered, washed several times with alcohol and water, and finally crystallised from alcohol in brown rectangular plates, m.p. 227-28°, yield 5 g. (Found: N, 8.84. $C_{14}H_{16}O_6N_2$ requires N, 9.09 per cent).

Reduction of the above compound (II): Formation of o-Aminocinnamic Acid.—The above compound (II, 4 g.) was mixed with strong hydrochloric acid and granulated tin, when the reaction commenced with evolution of heat. The mixture was allowed to stand for about 20 minutes and then heated under reflux for about 30 minutes, when a dark brown clear solution was obtained. The solution was diluted with water and tin completely removed by passing sulphuretted hydrogen. After filtration, the clear solution was evaporated to a small bulk when a crystalline product was obtained. It crystallised from water in colourless shining plates, m.p. 186-87° (decomp.), yield 0.5 g. (Found: N, 6.86. $C_9H_9O_2N, HCl$ requires N, 7.03 per cent).

The *free base* was obtained by adding sodium acetate to an aqueous solution of the above hydrochloride. The solid, thus obtained, crystallised from hot water in light yellow needles, m.p. 151-52° (decomp.) and its identity with *o*-aminocinnamic acid was confirmed by studying its properties and finally by analysis.

Condensation of Hippuric Acid with Anthranilic Acid: Formation of Anilide of Hippuric Acid and 1-Keto-3-benzoylaminomethyl-5:6-benzo-2:4-

oxazine (III).—An intimate mixture of hippuric acid (9 g.) and anthranilic acid (6.9 g.) was fused at 165-170° and the molten mass, mixed with finely powdered sodium acetate (6 g.), was heated at 145-150° for about 4 hours. On cooling, the fused mass was treated with aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution. The insoluble portion, the anilide of hippuric acid, was washed several times with water and was finally crystallised from alcohol in colourless plates, m.p. 207-208°, yield 4 g. (Found: N, 10.74. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{14}O_3N_2$; N, 11.02 per cent). Curtius (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1895, ii, 82, 257) obtained this compound (m.p. 208.5°) by the action of aniline on hippurazide. When it is heated with strong hydrochloric acid for about an hour, the solution yields on cooling and dilution with water a crystalline solid which is identified to be hippuric acid.

The bicarbonate solution, on acidification with excess of hydrochloric acid, yielded a solid which proved to be a mixture of the compound (III) and unreacted hippuric acid, from which the latter was removed by treating the solid several times with boiling water. The compound (III), which is sparingly soluble in hot water, was crystallised twice from alcohol in colourless slender needles, m.p. 205-207°, yield 2 g. [Found: N, 10.11. M.W (by titration with baryta), 282. $C_{16}H_{12}O_3N_2$ requires N, 10.0 per cent. M. W., 280]. When this compound is boiled for nearly 3 hours with strong hydrochloric acid, the solution on cooling and dilution with water, yields a solid identified to be hippuric acid. The mother-liquor, shaken several times with ether, yielded, on evaporation a crystalline solid identified to be anthranilic acid hydrochloride.

Condensation of the Compound (III) with o-Nitrobenzaldehyde: Formation of (IV, R = $C_6H_4NO_2$).—An acetic anhydride solution of equimolecular proportions of the compound (III) and *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde was heated under reflux in presence of fused sodium acetate for nearly 3 hours. On cooling the solution was treated with excess of aqueous sodium carbonate solution. The carbonate solution was filtered and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid, when a solid was obtained which crystallised from alcohol in brownish rectangular plates. It melts at 334-35° to a viscous red liquid. (Found: N, 10.04. $C_{23}H_{15}O_5N_3$ requires N, 10.17 per cent).

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